

Research Paper

Novel two-phase based cooling systems for fuel cell electric aircraft

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogen fuel cell powered propulsion is a promising option for shifting air travel to non-fossil fuel alternatives. However megawatt-scale fuel cells require large heat exchange surfaces for cooling, creating new challenges for efficient aircraft design. New, bespoke fuel cell cooling systems for aviation are required. This paper presents a novel cooling system for a fuel cell electric aircraft based on two-phase cooling with the natural refrigerant methanol. Three novel cooling systems are presented and evaluated by means of system simulation. The two-phase cooling systems comprise a pumped two-phase cooling circuit which is extended by a high-temperature refrigeration cycle. The effects inside the ram air channel and additional drags on the aircraft resulting from the cooling system as well as the influence of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect are analyzed. The novel two-phase based cooling systems are compared by means of system simulation. The comparison utilizes steady-state operating points as well as an example of a dynamic flight profile. Additionally, the usage of a variable air intake flap is discussed and evaluated. The variable intake flap ensures sufficient fuel cell cooling for high loads at take-off, and efficient cooling during cruise operation. The resulting best system architecture is a pumped two-phase cooling circuit extended by a high-temperature refrigeration cycle with coupled heat exchangers. This system ensures a critical fuel cell temperature for high heat production is not exceeded in take-off, and that a high cooling system efficiency is achieved during cruise operation while maintaining the fuel cell below 80 °C. This system is evaluated with the dynamic flight profile and the influence of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect is discussed. The thermodynamic process of the air inside the ram air channel is shown used to and describe how the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect reduces the cooling system drag. The core drag can be reduced by 65% during cruise operation.

1. Introduction

Man-made climate change is playing an ever-increasing role in everyday life as well as in current political and economic events [1,2]. Emissions of climate-warming accelerating greenhouse gases further intensify the effects of climate change. By the Paris Climate Agreement [3], many countries aim to keep global warming below 2 °C compared to the pre-industrial era. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions is a particularly important factor in meeting this target. Aviation contributes significantly to climate change, with 4% of global climate effects and 2.5% of CO₂-emissions attributed to this source [4]. With “Flight Path 2050” [5], the European Commission set the target in 2011 to reduce CO₂-emissions by 75% by 2050. In addition, nitrogen oxide emissions are set to be reduced by 90%.

In order to achieve the decarbonization of aviation, both a reduction in emissions from current propulsion technologies and completely alternative types of propulsion are required. In addition to alternatives such as purely battery-electric drives and Synthetic Aviation Fuels (SAFs), the use of hydrogen fuel in PEMFC is very promising. In addition to the possibility of operation with sustainably produced fuel, e.g. with so called green hydrogen [6], PEMFC have low noise and pollutant emissions, especially in comparison to hydrogen fueled turbine engines. Hydrogen fuel cell propulsion is estimated to potentially reduce the climate impact of aircraft by 75–90%, while a reduction of 50–75% is estimated with direct hydrogen combustion in gas turbines [7]. In general, electrified flying needs innovative thermal management concepts such as these used for hypersonic vehicles [8] or liquid cooling for eVOTL aircraft [9].

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Fig. 1. Energy flow diagram of the PEMFC, showing the percentage of the energy converted from chemical energy in the form of Hydrogen to electric energy and heat. The Energy flow diagram shows the necessity for a cooling system to dissipate heat to the environment (at about 80 °C) that is not dissipated by components such as the humidifier, extra reactants and through natural convection. Adapted from [10].

The high waste heat flow of the PEMFC poses a particular challenge. Fig. 1 shows the Sankey diagram [10] for the hydrogen fuel cell powered aircraft. A traditional kerosene powered turbofan converts approximately 45% of the chemical energy into propulsive power, while the same amount is dissipated as waste heat to the environment by exhaust gas. Using hydrogen in a fuel cell, about 50% of the provided chemical energy is converted to electrical energy. Excess hydrogen accounts for 5% and just as in the kerosene turbine, approximately 45% is waste heat. But while in a turbofan engine the waste heat can be mostly rejected within the turbine exhaust gas flow, for the fuel cell most of the waste heat needs to be rejected with the help of a dedicated cooling system. This is because the airflow directed through the fuel cell cathode is limited in order to minimize pressure drop and therefore only a small fraction of the waste heat is directly dissipated through the exhaust gas. Additionally, the PEMFC cooling system operates between 60 °C–80 °C, temperature levels that are much lower than the exhaust gas temperature of a turbofan. This results in relatively low driving temperature differences for heat transfer with the cooling air, resulting in the need for larger heat transfer areas.

Heinke et al. [11,12] described this challenge for fuel cell electric cars. They presented a high-temperature refrigerant cycle for increasing the temperature difference at the front-end heat exchanger. The increased temperatures result in increased cooling performance for challenging driving conditions at high ambient temperatures. As a result, the front-end heat exchanger requires to be designed larger. With the suggested high-temperature heat-pump the sizing could be kept and the heat rejection capability is increased by larger driving temperature differences. Otherwise, larger heat exchangers would cope with the design and construction space requirements for cars and not deteriorate the drag of the car. Träger [13] investigated on-board water recovery and spray cooling for improving the cooling performance at the front-end heat-exchanger. Wagenblast et al. [14] described the challenge of low temperature waste heat rejection for fuel cell driven heavy-duty trucks. They investigated spray cooling on real driving routes. This research focuses on optimizing the refrigerant system, understanding that the water supply for spray cooling could be very challenging for an aircraft.

Generally, there is a large power demand for an aircraft during take-off. For fuel cell electric aircraft, take-off necessitates a coinciding high cooling performance. During cruise the overall propulsion and cooling system must operate as efficiently as possible to achieve the targeted operation range [15]. Designing the fuel cell system suitable for satisfying the take-off power demands, when the necessity for large heat dissipation to the ambient requires a correspondingly large heat

transfer area, results in it being oversized during cruise. Because the large heat exchanger produces additional air resistance losses (drag), additional power is required and the most efficient point of operation for low power demand in cruise is not achieved [16]. To achieve efficient cruise operation, the heat exchanger should be designed to be slightly larger than needed for cruise. However, at take-off there are increased power requirements and lower driving temperature differences compared to cruise. This results in cooling requirements that a cooling system optimized for cruise operation cannot deliver. A possible solution to this design problem is to add a high-temperature refrigerant cycle to the cooling system to increase the driving temperature difference for heat rejection. Such a concept has been investigated for fuel cell electric vehicles [11,17,18].

Koschel et al. [19] investigated several pump-based two-phase cooling systems with methanol as a refrigerant for fuel cell electric aircraft. It was shown that two-phase cooling can reduce the required pump power by up to 99% and the required air mass flow for heat dissipation by 36% compared to liquid cooling. In addition, two-phase cooling achieves a more homogeneous temperature profile within the fuel cell. Kösters et al. [20] described an approach for a two-phase cooling system using a high-temperature vapor compression cycle (so called PCHP cooling) and water as a natural refrigerant. They used system simulation to compare the performance of PCHP cooling with water-based liquid cooling for a long-haul mission Airbus A320 equipped with a fuel cell jet engine hybrid drive. The authors found a significant potential for aircraft drag reduction during cruise due to the significantly smaller heat exchanger required by the PCHP cooling for heat transfer to the ambient, leading to a reduction of 16% in required propulsive power. However, the fuel cell system was considered to only cover the cruise power demand, requiring additional jet engines to provide the additional power demand during take-off. Furthermore, only a single, stationary operation point during cruise was examined. Therefore, it opens the research gap for this study.

This paper presents a novel cooling system for fuel cell electric aircraft including three main novel distributions. First, a pumped two-phase cooling system is extended by a switchable high-temperature refrigeration cycle for sufficient and efficient cooling in all flight phases. Second, three proposed cooling system architectures are compared at steady-state operation points and the best system is evaluated for a dynamic flight profile. Third, an evaluation of the drag reduction by the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect is performed.

This research uses the methanol based pumped two-phase cooling system proposed by Koschel et al. [19] as a baseline for comparison. In this research the idea of PCHP cooling [20] is applied to increase the cooling capacity at high power demands by extending the “Baseline System” with a high-temperature refrigeration cycle. The extended high-temperature refrigeration cycle can be switched on and off depending on the power demand to increase the cooling capacity. This flexibility of the proposed novel cooling systems allows for suitable cooling for different loads during the flight phases. A model-based comparison of different refrigerant-based cooling systems for fuel cell electric aircraft is performed. A physics based model for the ram air channel is described, including a detailed model of the refrigerant-air heat exchanger (in this case a condenser). This research compares three refrigerant-based two-phase cooling systems to assess their capability to provide sufficient fuel cell cooling during high heat loads and efficiency at lower heat loads. The first two-phase cooling system is a pumped circuit. The two other systems are extensions of the pumped circuit with different high-temperature refrigeration cycles. The extension is necessary to increase the cooling capacity for high heat loads. The system whose performance is deemed the best is then evaluated using a dynamic flight profile. The influence of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect and its effect on the drag reduction during different flight phases are described.

2. Methodology

A 1D-Modeling approach in Modelica programming language (version 4.0) [21] is used. In addition to the Modelica Standard Library, the TIL-libraries, library add-ons [22,23] and TILMedia-libraries [24,25] for describing the physics of the components and the systems behavior are applied. The Airbus A320-200 is selected as an example aircraft for this study [20].

2.1. Power requirements for an aircraft

The power required to move an aircraft is the result of the forces acting on the aircraft. Four forces are acting on an aircraft: Lift force (L), weight force (W), thrust force (F) and drag force (D). Depending on the flight phase, there are different ratios between the forces. During take-off or climb, the lift force is greater than the weight force and the thrust force is greater than the drag force. During cruise, there is an equilibrium of forces in which the lift and weight forces as well as the thrust and drag forces balance each other out. Under these conditions, the following equation relates the thrust force F , the weight force W and the ratio of lift force and drag force L/D :

$$F = \frac{W}{L/D} \quad (1)$$

In general the lift to drag ratio is dynamic. For this study it is simplified to the constant value for cruise flight. For the A320-200, the ratio of lift to drag force during cruise is $L/D = 16.3$ [26]. For an aircraft, different power requirements occur during different flight phases. For the A320-200 the average maximum power required during take-off is around $P = 20.72$ MW and the average power required during cruise is $P = 9.67$ MW [20]. For the calculation of the propulsion power, these powers are defined as the basic power requirement of the aircraft. The cooling system causes additional power losses, which are included in the calculation of the total electrical power. Also included are the drag losses for the cooling systems. Thus, the total power required consists of the basic power P and the additional power caused by the cooling system and is given by

$$P_{el,tot} = P + P_{Drag} + P_{Components} \quad (2)$$

where the required power of the cooling components, such as the pumps and compressors is represented by $P_{Components}$. The drag losses are described in Section 2.5.

2.2. Background on fuel cells for aviation and cooling

The electrical power output of a fuel cell is the product of cell current I_{fc} and cell voltage V_{fc} : $P_{fc} = I_{fc} * V_{fc}$. Assuming that the full electrical power demand corresponds to the fuel cell electrical power output at all times, the fuel cell heat output \dot{Q}_{fc} can be described as a function of the rated fuel cell power $P_{el,tot}$ and the fuel cell efficiency η_{fc} :

$$\dot{Q}_{fc} = \frac{1 - \eta_{fc}}{\eta_{fc}} * P_{el,tot} \quad (3)$$

The efficiency η_{fc} is dependent on the fuel cell operation point:

$$\eta_{fc} = \frac{V_{fc}}{V_{th}} \quad (4)$$

$V_{th} = 1.48$ V is the net cell reaction's thermoneutral voltage, derived from the higher heating value of hydrogen [24]. Any further influence of the fuel cell balance of plant components on overall electrical efficiency is left for future studies as the focus of this study is the relative performance comparison of phase change cooling topologies, which will not be significantly affected by the balance of plant parasitic power losses. To obtain a singular formula for fuel cell heat output as a function of operation point and scaled to $P_{el,tot}$, Eq. (3) can be expressed as

$$\dot{Q}_{fc} = \theta * P_{el,tot} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2. Simplified flight profile used for the analysis, consisting of the variables electrical power, airspeed and altitude over the flight time. Flight time is divided into five flight phases: Take-Off (TO), Climb, Cruise, Descent (Desc.) and Approach (AP).

where θ is an empirical formula for the non-dimensional fuel cell heat output as a function of the fuel cell utilization grade $x = P_{el}/P_{el,tot}$.

A polynomial regression on the voltage-current data is performed that was published by Pahon et al. [27] on a pristine 5 kW automotive PEMFC stack to create an empirical expression for θ . The original fuel cell performance data, the regression coefficients and a statement on the accuracy of the formula can be found in Appendix B.

For efficient and reliable operation of PEMFC, precise temperature management is mandatory. The conductivity of the ion exchange membrane increases with temperature, but is at the same time dependent on the presence of liquid water. If the water inside a PEM would evaporate completely, a severe increase in cell conductivity would follow, resulting not only in loss of performance, but also severe, irreversible degradation [28]. Therefore, a fuel cell temperature, as measured in the coolant outlet, of 80°C is typically maintained, although, for short periods of time coolant temperatures beyond 90°C may be tolerated. Because the coolant temperature across a fuel cell stack is not uniform and stack temperature variations of up to 10 K between coldest and hottest zones are typically anticipated, coolant temperatures beyond 80°C for an extended period of time must be avoided.

2.3. Flight mission: Dynamic flight profile

A simplified dynamic flight profile for a typical mid-range flight of an A320-200 was chosen. The flight profile consists of three variables. The main variable is the required electrical power of the aircraft. The model does not consider a direct conversion of energy to the propeller/fan. Instead, the required electrical power output of the fuel cell is specified. The electrical power represents the basic requirements of the aircraft and, as described above, is taken from the requirements of an A320-200 aircraft, which Kösters et al. [20] have summarized for take-off and cruise. A speed and altitude profile is derived from the performance profile. profile of the three variables of the flight profile is shown in Fig. 2.

2.4. Modeling of the ram air channel

The design of the ram air channel is crucial for the cooling of fuel cell electric aircraft. It provides the airflow needed for waste heat rejection. A schematic diagram is shown in Fig. 3. Four states (labeled 0, 1, 2 and 3 in Fig. 3) for the cooling air inside the ram air channel are described for the variables of state: Air pressure p , air speed w , and air temperature T . The variables of state as well as the cross-sectional area A are described along the ram air channel at each of the four components, namely, the air inlet, diffuser, heat exchanger and nozzle.

Fig. 3. Ram air channel modeling based on [29]. The model describes the variables of state of the air inside the ram air channel; pressure p , velocity w , temperature T as well as the cross-sectional area A for the diffuser (0–1), Air-HX (heat exchanger) (1–2) and nozzle (2–3).

The design of the air inlet (0) influences the flow conditions in the ram air channel duct. An example for air inlets are NACA-Ducts [30], which use sharp edges for braking up the laminar boundary layer and achieving relatively large air mass flow rates even at low velocities.

The diffuser (0 → 1) widens the cross-section. The airflow is decelerated and the speed reduction converts dynamic pressure into static pressure. For an ideal component, isentropic compression could be assumed.

In the next step the air flows through the heat exchanger (1 → 2), where the air absorbs the heat rejected from the refrigerant. The air temperature increases, resulting in a density decrease and velocity increase. Additionally, the air undergoes pressure losses in the heat exchanger. Those pressure losses are strongly dependent on the air velocity.

Finally the air flows through the nozzle (2 → 3), where the cross-section is decreased, causing the pressure to decrease while the air speed increases. The enthalpy difference over the heat exchanger is converted into thrust. The Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect can be utilized at the nozzle to produce additional thrust if the air velocity increases over the whole ram air channel. The ram air channel can be described as an open Joule process. [31,32].

2.4.1. Variable air inlet flap of the diffuser

The adjustability of the air inlet flap of the diffuser is little studied in the literature. In general, there is limited literature on air ducts and heat exchangers in aviation as no dedicated heat exchanger is required for modern jet engines. The existing literature mostly refers to aircraft from the time of the Second World War [32–34]. Due to electrification and hybridization, the heat exchanger in the powertrain is becoming increasingly relevant in current investigations [35].

The ram air channel consists of the diffuser and nozzle components, as well as the heat exchanger installed in the ram air channel. The nozzle is an adjustable element in previous systems and is used to adapt the static air pressure at the outlet of the nozzle to the ambient pressure. As an extension, the effect of a adjustable air inlet flap on the diffuser is being investigated. The air inlet flap defines the opening cross-section of the diffuser. In the model, this is defined by the ratio between the inlet cross-section and the outlet cross-section of the diffuser A_0/A_1 . The flight phases shown result in different power requirements for the cooling system and, therefore also different air mass flow rates. A

high air mass flow rate is required for heat dissipation at high power requirements and, conversely, a low air mass flow rate is required for low power requirements. However, a high air mass flow rate also means a high pressure loss via the heat exchanger and therefore “drag” losses. As a result, a high cross-sectional ratio is required for the lowest possible fuel cell temperature at high power requirements in take-off phase, whereas a lower cross-sectional ratio is required in cruise at correspondingly lower power requirements in order to minimize fuel consumption.

2.4.2. Calculation of state variables inside the ram air channel

The calculation of the state variables (p , w , T) is based on the assumption of an isentropic change of state. Using the energy theorem [36] (Eq. (A.1)) the state variables of the ram air channel can be calculated. The derivation of the necessary equations is shown in Appendix A. The resulting equation for the lossy pressure difference over the diffuser, which describes the correlations between pressure and velocity, is given by the following:

$$(p_1 - p_0) = \eta_{diff} * p_{t,0} * \left(\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_1^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_0^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} \right) \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the equation for the nozzle and the lossy pressure difference also derived in Appendix A, is given by:

$$(p_3 - p_2) = \frac{p_{t,2}}{\eta_{noz}} * \left(\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_3^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_2^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} \right) \quad (7)$$

The temperatures at the given state points are calculated from the first law of thermodynamics as seen in Eq. (A.18).

For the diffuser, the outlet pressure and temperature are calculated based on the set ratio of inlet and outlet area A_0/A_1 , and thus the resulting velocities. For the nozzle the outlet velocity and temperature are calculated such that the outlet pressure is equal to the ambient air pressure.

2.5. Drag calculation for the cooling system

The drag losses associated with the fuel cell system P_{Drag} can be further subdivided into four areas, namely core drag D_{core} , subpressure drag D_{sub} , external drag D_{ext} and mass drag D_{mass} :

$$P_{Drag} = w_0 * (D_{core} + D_{sub} + D_{ext} + D_{mass}) \quad (8)$$

2.5.1. Core drag

The core drag describes the irreversibilities and resulting energy losses that occur within the flow by applying the momentum theorem [37]. The nozzle is modeled with variable geometry so that the air pressure at the outlet at the nozzle corresponds to the ambient pressure due to complete expansion. The velocity losses are caused by the pressure losses in the heat exchanger and in the ram air channel. Thus, the core drag is given by:

$$D_{core} = \dot{m}_{core} * (w_3 - w_0) \quad (9)$$

The core drag also includes the influence of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect [31]. The Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect describes how the enthalpy increase in the heat exchanger can result in a higher outlet velocity of the nozzle. On the one hand, this is achieved in part by reducing the air density, which results in a higher flow velocity at a constant mass flow rate.

In addition, the isentropic expansion via the nozzle (see Fig. 3 (2 → 3)) can be used to convert an increased temperature difference, and thus enthalpy difference, into velocity (see Eq. (A.18), (A.19)). The influence of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect can be described by the velocity difference between heated and unheated outlet air [20]:

$$D_{MRJE} = \dot{m}_{core} * (w_{3,h} - w_{3,uh}) \quad (10)$$

The Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect reduces the drag loss so that thrust can be generated under ideal conditions.

2.5.2. Subpressure drag

Furthermore, the subpressure drag describes the losses due to the possible pressure difference with the ambient pressure at the outlet of the nozzle [20].

$$D_{sub} = A_3 * (p_3 - p_0) \quad (11)$$

This can be caused by overexpansion in the nozzle. If the static pressure is lowered below the ambient pressure by the nozzle, the outflowing air is correspondingly underpressurized. To compensate for the pressure difference, ambient air flows to the outlet of the nozzle, creating a braking effect for the aircraft in the form of drag. In the assumptions for this study, the outlet pressure is set to be the same as the inlet pressure and therefore subpressure drag does not occur.

2.5.3. External drag

The external drag D_{ext} summarizes the air resistance caused by the heat exchanger nacelle [37]. This depends on the size and positioning of the heat exchanger and is given by:

$$D_{ext} = c_D * \frac{\rho}{2} * w_0^2 * A_{front} \quad (12)$$

where A_{front} describes the representative cross-sectional area, also known as the shadow area, of the air application point. The cross-sectional area used depends on the heat exchanger's general positioning on the aircraft. If the heat exchanger is positioned externally on the wing, the shadow area corresponds to the front surface of the heat exchanger. Assuming that the heat exchanger is positioned within the aircraft fuselage, the shadow area is considered to be either the diffuser's inlet cross-section or the nozzle's outlet cross-section. For the purpose of this paper, A_{front} corresponds with the cross-sectional area of the heat exchanger. The drag coefficient c_D is dynamic in reality, but is assumed to be constant here. In [38] a range of possible c_D values is given. There it is assumed that the ram air channel is installed either in combination with the fuel cell and the drive unit as a nacelle, or in the aircraft fuselage. As a result, only part of the front surface of the heat exchanger affects the external drag. For this reason, a low drag coefficient of $c_D = 0.06$ is assumed.

2.5.4. Mass drag

The mass drag summarizes the influence of the combined mass of the additional components required for the cooling system [37]. It is calculated in the same way the power requirement is determined in the equilibrium state and is given by:

$$D_{mass} = \frac{m * g}{L/D} \quad (13)$$

The consideration of the mass depends on the set system limit. The system limit includes all components that are required for the pure cooling system of the fuel cell. This includes, for example, all pumps and compressors, the coolant or refrigerant and the heat exchanger itself.

2.6. Design and modeling of the heat exchanger

The aim of the design of the refrigerant-air heat exchanger is to enable a suitable waste heat dissipation from the fuel cell during operation of an electric aircraft. The considered aircraft corresponds to

the dimensions of an Airbus A320-200 [20]. For this size of an aircraft, thrust power outputs of up to 20 MW are required. With the implementation of the cooling system, there will be an additional requirement for electrical power due to the compressor and pumps as well as the induced drag. The additional power required for the heat exchanger is estimated to be 5 MW. With the efficiency of the fuel cell described in Section 2.2 and the maximum load of the fuel cell occurring during take-off, the thermal output roughly equals the electric output. The heat exchanger needs to be optimized for a minimum frontal cross-section area, pressure drop and weight as all of these factors produce drag. For the design of the heat exchanger, the simplified flight profile described in Section 2.3 was used with the boundary conditions that occur at the maximum load point or at the point at which the ratio between fuel cell waste heat and transferable heat to the ambient air is greatest. This design point is in the take-off phase. During take-off, the airspeed and thus the maximum air speed at the inlet of the ram air channel is 76 m/s. The ambient air temperature is assumed to be a maximum of 40 °C at a static air pressure of 1.013 bar. The aim of the heat exchanger design is to limit the fuel cell temperature to 80 °C. With the temperature of the cooling fluid at the heat exchanger outlet being just below the fuel cell temperature and a pinch point of 5 K, the maximum temperature of the cooling fluid is set to be 75 °C.

The first step is to estimate the dimensions of the heat exchanger. To estimate the minimum air-side frontal area A of the heat exchanger, the required air mass flow is first determined using the heat capacity. The heat transfer capacity $k * A$ of the air-side can then be used to determine the required transfer area. Based on these two parameters, a specific heat exchanger can then be dimensioned. First, the required air mass flow rate is calculated, which is necessary for ideal heat transfer in order to dissipate the waste heat from the fuel cell. The heat exchanger is designed as a cross-counterflow heat exchanger so that the outlet temperature of the air is raised to the inlet temperature of the refrigerant, taking into account the pinch point temperature difference. The required air mass flow is calculated for a heat flow of 25 MW that is assumed for take-off. The ambient temperature is assumed to be 40 °C, representing a worst case scenario at the airport runway. A temperature difference of $\Delta T = 75 \text{ °C} - 40 \text{ °C} = 35 \text{ °C}$ and a specific heat capacity of the air at 40 °C of $c_p = 1.007 \text{ kJ}/(\text{kg K})$ can be determined, resulting in a mass flow rate of

$$\dot{m} = \frac{25 \text{ MW}}{1.007 \text{ kJ}/(\text{kg K}) * 35 \text{ K}} = 709.32 \text{ kg/s} \quad (14)$$

For the given conditions, an air mass flow rate of 709.32 kg/s is therefore required. The cross-sectional area A can be then determined from

$$A = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho * w} \quad (15)$$

The air density under the given conditions is $\rho_{air} = 1.23 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$. The velocity w of the air at the inlet of the heat exchanger depends on the cross-sectional ratio of the diffuser in the ram air channel. The cross-sectional ratio is variable, but is limited during operation by a fixed maximum velocity $w = 45 \text{ m/s}$ in order to protect the heat exchanger from damage. The minimum required cross-sectional area resulting from the assumptions is calculated as:

$$A = \frac{709.32 \text{ kg/s}}{1.23 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3 * 45 \text{ m/s}} = 12.81 \text{ m}^2 \quad (16)$$

The required cross-sectional area is applied along a dynamic flight profile is applied to ensure the heat exchanger is designed for the largest cooling requirement.

The flight profile defines the air temperature and air pressure, speed, and the required power. The resulting required frontal area of the heat exchanger under the boundary conditions used for the calculation is shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the maximum frontal area is only required directly at take-off. With increasing airspeed w and decreasing ambient air temperature T and a constant mass flow rate,

Fig. 4. Required frontal area A of the heat exchanger as a function of the flight profile (see Fig. 2) obtained by calculating the front surface area according to Eq. (15) and the boundary conditions during the flight, namely, waste heat flow \dot{Q} , velocity w , air temperature T and static air pressure p . The temperature difference corresponds to the difference between 75°C and the current air temperature.

Table 1

Pressure loss and heat transfer correlations used within the simulation models of the heat exchanger from the TIL libraries [22].

	Air	Condensation	Evaporation
Pressure loss	Kim and Bullard [40]	Swamee and Jain [41]	Swamee and Jain [41]
Heat transfer	Park and Jacobi [42]	Shah [43]	Shah and Chen [44]

the heat transfer rate increases. High-temperature refrigeration cycles can potentially increase the driving temperature difference between air and coolant and thereby reduce the required frontal area.

To explore this possibility, the heat transfer area for forced convection is estimated. A constant value of $200 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ K})$ [39] is assumed for the heat transfer coefficient α of the air. Calculating for the heat transfer area A results in:

$$A_{Air} = \frac{\dot{Q}}{\alpha * \Delta T} = \frac{25 \text{ MW}}{200 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ K}) * 35 \text{ K}} = 3571.43 \text{ m}^2 \quad (17)$$

The specific heat exchanger was designed on the basis of the estimated frontal and heat transfer areas. In order to use the advantage of counterflow heat exchangers and enable the entire temperature difference between air and cooling fluid to be utilized, the heat exchanger is divided into several layers. The geometry of the air and refrigerant side of the heat exchanger were optimized by performing parametric studies. A frontal area is selected that is slightly smaller than the previously calculated one, as an increased temperature difference is anticipated by using a high-temperature refrigeration cycle in most examined cooling architectures. The frontal area is therefore assumed to be 10 m^2 . This results from a compromise between the lowest achievable fuel cell temperature and the lowest required electrical power of the overall system. The applied correlations for pressure loss and heat transfer are listed in Table 1.

2.7. Description of two-phase cooling PEMFC

In this study, methanol is used as the refrigerant for cooling directly inside the fuel cell [19]. Methanol has an Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP) of zero and no Global Warming Potential (GWP). Also, the electrical conductivity is negligibly low, which is important for direct use within the fuel cell stack.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the refrigerants methanol, n-butane and R1233zd(E) based on the position of the wet vapor region on the pressure-enthalpy diagram including the 80°C isotherm.

A comparison of methanol, n-butane and R1233zd(E) is shown in the $p-h$ -diagram in Fig. 5. The 80°C isotherm corresponds to the fuel cell cooling temperature. It can be seen that the evaporating pressures for methanol are lower compared to the other refrigerants. Also, the vaporization enthalpy of methanol is larger and consequently less refrigerant mass flow is necessary for cooling.

For operation at 80°C the pressure of methanol is slightly above atmospheric pressure. This results in lower requirements for pressure protection in the fuel cell, compared to the use of other refrigerants, whose operating pressures are many times higher.

The methanol-based pumped two-phase cooling system can be extended by a high-temperature refrigeration cycle for heat rejection. Additionally, a compressor loop is added to the coolant loop with pumps. The goal of compression is to reach higher temperature levels for two-phase heat rejection. However, the temperature in the wet vapor area is not the same as the compressor outlet temperature. For methanol in particular this results in limitations. If the temperature level is to be raised from 80°C to 120°C , a compressor outlet temperature of around 205°C is reached. The compressor discharge temperature is crucial in regard to the oil used for compressor lubrication and temperatures this high could lead to degraded lubricating performance. The discussion on oil in the refrigerant cycle for fuel cell cooling will not be pursued further in this study. There are already some developments on oil-free compressors, described in the literature [45,46], but further research in the area is necessary.

The refrigerant used for the fuel cell should not evaporate completely [47]. Complete evaporation or even superheating results in a tremendous loss of cooling performance and is associated with an intolerable increase in temperature. A maximum vapor quality of 30% is targeted as loss of cooling performance occurs at higher vapor qualities and dry spots could result inside the cooling channels [19]. Experimental studies found the best cooling performance corresponds to a maximum vapor quality of approximately 30% [48].

2.8. Two-phase cooling systems

The cooling systems and the ram air channel are connected by the refrigerant-air heat exchanger (condenser). For some systems the condenser is divided into two parts on the refrigerant side. The air-side of the condenser is always the same size. All systems use refrigerant pumps and an accumulator. Additionally, an expansion valve (EXV) or a directional valve (DV) is necessary for systems using a compressor.

Koschel et al. [19] used the fuel cell model from the TIL libraries [22] and modified it for two-phase cooling. This complex fuel cell model was originally described by Tang et al. [49,50]. For this study a simplified fuel cell model is derived for purposes of focusing

Fig. 6. “Baseline System”, pumped two-phase cooling system using two pumps, adapted from Koschel et al. [19].

Fig. 7. Pressure-enthalpy diagram of the baseline pumped two-phase cooling system using two pumps.

on the cooling system. The fuel cell is modeled by a thermal capacity representing the mass and a heat source rejecting the waste heat that is calculated based on the efficiency. The cooling plate is simplified as a bundle of tubes where the refrigerant absorbs the heat. Methanol is used as the refrigerant and is evaporated directly inside the cooling channels of the fuel cell.

2.8.1. Baseline system

The “Baseline System” is a pumped two-phase cooling circuit shown in Fig. 6. The circuit consists of the fuel cell, the condenser block, an accumulator and two pumps. The first pump is positioned upstream of the fuel cell. It draws liquid refrigerant from the accumulator and pumps it through the fuel cell. In the fuel cell, the refrigerant absorbs heat and partially evaporates. The speed of the pump is used as the control variable. The controlled variable is the vapor quality at the outlet of the fuel cell. This is set to a constant 30% [19].

In the second path, the pump (pump 2) is positioned downstream of the condenser. In the path of pump 2, gaseous refrigerant is drawn out of the accumulator which then liquefies in the condenser. The amount of refrigerant delivered by the pump should be controlled to ensure there is still sub-cooling at the outlet of the condenser. The pump is control to maintain a constant sub-cooling of 5 K.

Fig. 7 shows the operation of the system on a Enthalpy-pressure diagram. The dashed lines represent the partial circuit via the condenser and the solid lines the partial circuit via the fuel cell.

The advantages of this cooling system stems from its low complexity and, above all, the low refrigerant mass flow rate required. The latent heat of the refrigerant can be utilized. In addition, a uniform temperature distribution is achieved across the fuel cell. However, the

Fig. 8. System configuration with pumped methanol circuits, extended by a high-temperature refrigeration cycle for high load cooling requirements and heat rejection at a higher temperature level in condenser 2.

circuit is limited by the driving temperature difference between the refrigerant and the ambient air at a given mass flow of ambient air. In contrast to liquid cooling, where the coolant should be 5 K–10 K colder than the fuel cell, a temperature difference of 2 K–3 K is sufficient when using refrigerants to dissipate the necessary heat. At high ambient temperatures, however, there is a relatively low temperature difference in the ambient condenser and increased air mass flow rates would be required. But, the air mass flow rate is limited by the geometry of the air duct and the speed of the aircraft. In order to increase the driving temperature difference the baseline pump system is therefore extended by a high temperature refrigeration cycle in the next step. This option has been investigated for fuel cell electric cars [11,17].

2.8.2. Extended-system

To extend the capacity range of the cooling system, a high-temperature refrigeration cycle using a compressor is added to the existing “Baseline System” (comparable to [11,12,17]). The pumped circuit is capable of independently cooling the fuel cell up to a certain level of waste heat and the high-temperature refrigeration cycle is only switched on when cooling requirements increase beyond this level. To ensure this functionality, the two circuits are coupled via the accumulator.

The corresponding system configuration is shown in Fig. 8. The compressor draws in a part of the gaseous refrigerant and compresses it to a higher pressure level. At the higher pressure and respectively higher temperature level, heat is dissipated to the ambient air via condenser 2. The liquefied refrigerant is then expanded to the low pressure level via the EXV and returned to the accumulator together with the mass flow of the pumped circuit.

By coupling via the accumulator, the high-temperature refrigeration cycle removes heat from the refrigerant, thereby reducing the enthalpy of the methanol in the accumulator. The fuel cell continues to be supplied by the pumped circuit via pump 1. The overall condenser is divided, so that each subsystem uses a part of the condenser. On the air-side, the two condensers are connected in series, with the temperature of the air entering condenser 2 having already been increased in condenser 1. Due to the increased temperature of the refrigerant after the compression, however, a greater driving temperature difference can

Table 2
Summary of the steady-state boundary conditions of the various flight phases: take-off, climb, cruise, descent and approach.

Phase	T_{amb} °C	p_{air} bar	Velocity m/s	Elevation m	Power MW
Take-Off	40	1.013	76	1	20.7
Climb	10	0.570	150	4500	15.0
Cruise	-25	0.200	231	10,000	9.7
Descent	0	0.470	203	6000	2.5
Approach	30	0.900	133	800	10.0

Fig. 9. Pressure-enthalpy diagram for system configuration with a pumped two-phase cooling circuit extended by a high-temperature refrigeration cycle using a compressor for high load cooling requirements.

Fig. 10. “Extended Coupled System” configuration for methanol refrigerant cooling with the option of connecting the condenser parts from pumped two-phase cooling circuit and high-temperature refrigeration cycle for more efficient operation in pump-only mode.

be achieved in the downstream condenser. Overall, a greater heat flow is possible for a constant mass flow rate of air.

The pumped circuit is controlled as in the “Baseline System” described above. In the high-temperature refrigeration cycle the compressor speed is used to control the fuel cell temperature and the EXV control ensures a certain subcooling downstream of Condenser 2. This allows the mass flow rate to be controlled to a minimum level that is sufficient to release the maximum possible amount of heat to the environment. The resulting circuit in the ph diagram is shown in Fig. 9.

A disadvantage of this cooling system arises at low and medium loads. If the compressor is switched off, condenser 2 cannot be used for cooling. However, due to the air-side series connection of the two condensers, air continues to flow through both condensers, causing pressure losses on the air-side.

2.8.3. Extended coupled system

To address the operational issue described in the previous section for low and medium loads, a further design modification is proposed. An additional three-way DV is integrated to couple the pumped two-phase cooling circuit and high-temperature refrigeration cycle for certain operating points (Fig. 10). The coupling enables a full usage of both condensers in all operating conditions and therefore, an increased cooling capacity in pump mode (i.e., low and medium load operation where the additional cooling capability is not needed). By using both condensers, the entire heat transfer area of the condenser block can be utilized, allowing more heat to be transferred to the ambient air. As a result, compressor operation is only necessary for higher performance requirements and resulting heat loads. If only the pumped circuit is used, the electrical power required is reduced. Furthermore, the increased cooling capacity means the pumped circuit can be used for a larger range of operating points, resulting overall in more efficient cooling system performance.

The control of the other components of the “Extended Coupled System” is the same as the control of the “Extended System” described above.

3. Results and discussion

First we give a brief evaluation of the variable cross-sectional ratio for the inlet flap. Then results from a comparison in steady-state operation as well as an analysis in a dynamic flight operation are discussed.

The cross-sectional ratio for each point of operation in the flight profile (Section 2.3) is optimized. In order to avoid creating a negative pressure at the outlet of the heat exchanger, the opening cross-section of the diffuser is limited to a maximum allowed value. However, the minimum opening cross-section is defined by the minimum air mass flow rate required for sufficient cooling of the fuel cell in cruise operation. The maximum cross-sectional ratio designed for take-off is selected to be $A_0/A_1 = 0.37$, while the minimum cross-sectional ratio designed for the cruise is selected to be $A_0/A_1 = 0.17$.

3.1. Cooling system comparison in steady-state operation

For the steady-state comparison two out of five operation points from the flight profile (Fig. 2) are evaluated. Table 2 provides the relevant parameters for the five points of operation, corresponding to take-off, climb, cruise, descent and approach.

The highest performance requirements are present during take-off, characterized by low speed and high ambient temperature and pressure. This poses the greatest challenge for the cooling system. The second evaluation point is the climb. In the climb, high demands continue to be placed on the cooling system. There is an increased electrical power requirement and thus waste heat in order to both accelerate and reach the flight altitude. In addition, the driving temperature difference for heat transfer increases as the temperature of the ambient air decreases with altitude. Less power is required in cruise flight. The power requirements result from the constant cruising speed and altitude. Depending on the total flight duration, a large part of the flight is completed in cruise. To minimize overall energy consumption, it is therefore important to minimize the power requirements during this phase of the flight. Descent is characterized by low power requirements as altitude and speed are reduced. No additional thrust is required. During the approach phase, the aircraft may take off again and therefore requires more power, however due to the continued higher altitude and

Fig. 11. Fuel cell temperature comparison for take-off and cruise operation.

Fig. 12. System comparison for required cooling power due to drag and additional power needed for compressor and pump during take-off and cruise operation.

Fig. 13. Average temperature of the PEMFC in the simplified dynamic flight profile, divided into the flight phases Take-Off (TO), Climb, Cruise, Descent (Desc.) and Approach (AP).

speed during approach, lower power requirements are placed on the cooling system than during take-off. The requirements of the five flight phases show that take-off and cruise are particularly decisive for the design and evaluation.

Fig. 11 shows the resulting fuel cell temperatures for steady state evaluation of the three cooling systems in take-off and cruise operation. It can be seen that the lowest temperature of the fuel cell can be achieved with the “Extended Coupled System”. The temperatures for the “Extended System” and “Extended Coupled System” in take-off are acceptable, while the temperature for the “Baseline System” during take-off would be much too high.

Fig. 12 shows a comparison of the additional power requirements for cooling of the three system architectures which result from additional drag produced by the cooling system and the power needed by

Fig. 14. Shares of core drag, external drag and mass drag in the total drag caused by the cooling system over the course of the dynamic flight profile.

the cooling system components (compressor + pumps). During take-off the “Baseline System” is much more efficient than other cooling systems, but as it does not achieve the temperature requirements, this design is not suitable. The “Extended System” and “Extended Coupled System” result in nearly the same power requirements. In cruise operation the “Extended coupled System” is the most efficient. Compared to the “Extended System”, the advantage of this system is that the high-temperature refrigeration cycle is linked to the pumped two-phase cooling circuit. In addition, both condensers (Fig. 10) are coupled in cruise when only the pumped circuit is active, so that more waste heat can be dissipated to the ambient air.

3.2. System analysis in dynamic operation

The “Extended Coupled System” architecture is identified as best suited for the cooling requirements of the application and therefore is further evaluated in the system analysis for dynamic operation. This analysis follows the simplified previously determined dynamic flight profile in Fig. 2. The fuel cell temperature over flight operation is depicted in Fig. 13. It can be seen that at the beginning of the flight profile (TO), where the highest performance requirements occur, the target temperature of 80 °C cannot be maintained. However the temperature can be kept below 105 °C, which may be acceptable for a short operational time during [51]. As the flight duration progresses and the speed increases accordingly, a higher heat flow can be released into the ambient air, which enables the fuel cell temperature to be reduced to the target value.

In pump operation, the compressor is switched off so that the set-point temperature of the air flap is set via the control system. According to the flight profile, most of the flight duration is spent in cruise. As pump operation is sufficient in this flight phase, less power is required for the components and a lower air mass flow is required due to the air flap setting.

This has an effect on the resulting core drag as can be seen from Eq. (9). The variation of the different drag losses with flight phase is shown in Fig. 14. The mass drag remains constant over the entire flight phase, as the fuel in the model is not considered. With a constant drag coefficient c_D , the external drag is only dependent on the airspeed and air density (see Eq. (12)). Therefore, only the core drag is influenced by the cooling system.

The core drag is dependent on the air mass flow rate and the air velocity difference between the inlet and outlet of the ram air channel (see Eq. (9)). The air mass flow rate is set in the system via the diffuser air flap. By assuming that the inlet velocity of the air in the diffuser always corresponds to the airspeed, the mass flow rate results from the cross-sectional ratio of the diffuser. The air is slowed down via the diffuser, whereby the dynamic pressure of the air is

Fig. 15. Temperature-Entropy diagram of the air in the ram air channel in the dynamic flight profile at take-Off ($t = 20$ s), Climb ($t = 10$ min) and Cruise ($t = 1$ h).

converted into static air pressure. The greater the cross-sectional ratio, the greater the velocity difference and thus the pressure difference. As the ambient pressure is to be restored at the outlet of the nozzle, the air pressure must at least be increased via the diffuser to compensate for the pressure loss across the heat exchanger.

The difference in velocity that can be recovered can be read from the temperature-entropy diagram of the air. The temperature difference can be converted into an enthalpy difference using Eq. (A.19), which in turn can be converted into a velocity difference using Eq. (A.18).

Fig. 15 shows the temperature-entropy diagram for the process along the ram air channel at three points of flight: Take-off (20 s), climb (10 min) and cruise (1 h). The entropy increase is clearly visible due to the losses in the diffuser and the nozzle. It can also be seen that the pressure losses (seen e.g. in climb) via the condenser result in a lower temperature difference across the nozzle. This means that the air outlet velocity of the nozzle is lower than the airspeed and therefore drag losses occur in the form of core drag. High core drag occurs particularly at the beginning of the flight profile. The increased power requirements at take-off, the low speeds in relation to cruise and the high air density contribute to an increase in core drag.

Returning to Fig. 14 the black line along the top of the core drag region indicates the total drag. The constant mass drag and the increasing external drag with increasing speed can be seen. It is noticeable that the external drag initially rises sharply during the climb, only to fall again at the start of the cruise. This is due to the fact that the cruising speed is reached before the cruising altitude. As the temperature and pressure of the ambient air decreases due to the increasing altitude, the air density also decreases, which has a linear influence on the external drag. During take-off (TO) and climb, core drag makes up the largest proportion of total drag.

Just prior to the transition from Climb to Cruise that occurs at 0.4 hours, the total drag (shown as the black line at top of the shaded “Core Drag” area) in Fig. 14 is decreasing slightly. At the transition, the total drag levels off for approximately 0.2 hours at a value of approximately 30 kN, before decreasing abruptly and stabilizing at a new steady-state value 25 kN that persists throughout the remainder of the Cruise portion of flight. The switchover point at which the high-temperature refrigeration cycle is switched off and the temperature of the fuel cell is regulated via the air flap of the diffuser is clearly visible and occurs at the transition between Climb and Cruise. By lowering the air mass flow rate, the core drag is significantly reduced. It is also noticeable that shortly after the start of descent, the total drag is lower than the sum of mass drag and external drag. In this area of operation, an increase in speed is achieved along the ram air channel so that the core drag is negative and thrust is generated. This can be attributed to a combination of the low waste heat output, the low ambient temperature and the high airspeed. Due to the low waste heat output and the high-temperature difference between the ambient

Fig. 16. Drag caused by the cooling system with the respective proportions of core drag, external drag and mass drag. In addition, the additional drag that would be present without the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect is shown as the dark shaded area above. The line representing the total drag when the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect is considered.

air and the fuel cell, only a very low air mass flow rate is required. To achieve this, the air flap of the diffuser is nearly closed, resulting in a high cross-sectional ratio. The high cross-sectional ratio leads to an increased static air pressure in front of the condenser and thus to a higher air density. Overall, only a very low pressure loss is caused by the condenser, but a higher outlet velocity can be achieved via the nozzle due to the high specific enthalpy increase.

The Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect plays a decisive role when considering losses via the ram air channel. The possibility of reducing the air mass flow rate makes the effect all the more significant, as the specific enthalpy increases with a lower mass flow rate and the pressure loss decreases.

In the following, the influence of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect on the drag losses will be examined. The Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect is described with the velocity difference between heated and unheated air mass flow rate. In order to simulate the influence, an assumed second ram air channel is implemented in parallel to the ram air channel containing the cooling system, which imitates the pressure losses via the condenser, but eliminates the velocity and enthalpy increase through the condenser. The velocity at the outlet of the nozzle of the second ram air channel is used as a reference for the air velocity $w_{3,uh}$. The equation for the core drag (Eq. (9)) shows that a considerable reduction in the difference between airspeed and exit velocity of the nozzle is achieved for the heated air mass flow rate and thus produces a reduction in the core drag.

Fig. 16 represents the absolute reduction in drag losses. For this purpose, the influence of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect is shown via the dynamic flight profile. As a reference, the proportions of drag shown previously (see also Fig. 14) are shown. It can be seen that there is a particularly large effect in Climb and Cruise. As the airspeed decreases and the electrical power required decreases, the influence of the effect also decreases. Due to the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect, the core drag can be reduced by 10% to 40% during take-off and climb and by up to 65% during cruise. By the end of the cruise, the total drag of the cooling system can be reduced by around 15%.

4. Conclusions and outlook

As part of this work, a model of the cooling system of an aircraft with fuel cell propulsion was developed and used to simulate the thermal management of an Airbus A320-200 in a typical mid-range operation. The objective of this work was to develop and compare system architectures for aircraft fuel cell cooling using phase-change cooling. Also the effects of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect are described. For this purpose, a model of an air duct through which the ambient air is directed to the heat exchanger was developed. The heat exchanger

is designed and parameterized for the application of a refrigerant-air heat exchanger acting as a condenser for heat rejection in a pumped two-phase cooling circuit or the extension by a high-temperature refrigeration cycle. Three refrigerant-based cooling system architectures with the natural refrigerant methanol were investigated. The “Baseline System”, “Extended System”, “Extended Coupled System” architectures were investigated for steady-state operating points, and the “Extended Coupled System” architecture was evaluated further for a simplified dynamic flight profile.

All systems use the same condenser dimensions, thereby enabling a direct comparison of the results. The systems were used to investigate the influence of diffuser air flap adjustability on cooling system functionality. The study shows that an adjustable air flap has significant advantages over a constant air flap geometry. Depending on the cross-sectional ratio of the constant air flap, a reduction of approximately 60% in drag losses can be achieved at cruising speed. This results in an electrical power requirement reduction of 10% in cruise, and enables the fuel cell temperature to be kept below the maximum allowable temperature during take-off. To enable both of these desirable effects, an adjustable air flap on the diffuser is thus used for the subsequent comparison of the systems.

In general, the design of a cooling system is a compromise between cooling effectiveness and efficiency. At high take-off loads, uncompromised effectiveness is most important; the fuel cell temperature must be kept within a specified range in all conditions. However, at lower loads, such as during cruise, the cooling system must operate as efficiently as possible to reduce system energy consumption and to meet range targets. The results show that a pumped two-phase cooling circuit extended by a high-temperature refrigeration cycle with coupled heat exchangers (“Extended Coupled System”) architecture can meet both, high load effectiveness targets and low load efficiency targets. The investigation of the Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect shows that in cruise operation when efficiency is most important, the core drag is reduced significantly, due to this effect.

This research indicates a need for further investigation into two-phase cooling systems for fuel cell electric aircraft using methanol as the refrigerant. To advance this field of study, future research should focus on investigating and validating the heat transfer characteristics and empirical correlations for methanol [19]. Additionally, the use of methanol in a high-temperature refrigeration cycle within the PEMFC stack necessitates the incorporation of an oil-free compressor, suitable for the refrigerant methanol [46].

Furthermore a next step should be the implementation of a detailed fuel cell balance of plant model as described in the Refs. [49,50]. Petersen et al. [52] presented a comprehensive fuel cell system model developed in Modelica and TIL [22]. This model incorporates peripheral energy consumers such as the air compressor and re-circulation fan. Incorporating this intricate model can enhance the precision of the current model and facilitate investigations of multiple cross-couplings. The knowledge of spray cooling for fuel cell-electric trucks [14] should also be applied and evaluated for an aircraft.

Hydrogen, which is transported in cryogenic form, can also be employed for the dissipation of waste heat from the fuel cell. The implementation of a system designated as rCEUS [53] has the potential to recuperate technical work, resulting in reduced power requirements for the fuel cell. This could result in a reduction in dimensions of the air-side condenser. An additional option for minimizing the size of the condenser is to utilize the outer shell of the aircraft as a transfer surface [54].

Another approach for an attractive compromise between take-off effectiveness and cruise efficiency could be the employment of a hydrofluoroolefin-based heat pump cycle, rejecting fuel cell waste heat into a singular, small condenser. Increased efficiency penalties particularly during take-off can be expected, due to the architecture’s reliance on a large heat pump temperature lift during take-off, but the potential

for efficiency improvements during cruise is higher. Furthermore, such a cooling architecture is realizable with current compressor technology and may be especially attractive for long-range flights due to minimized condenser drag losses [55].

The SKAiB project is focused on optimizing the two-phase cooling system for a scaled fuel cell electric aircraft [56]. Additionally, experimental investigations are being conducted to examine heat transfer during evaporation within a single fuel cell channel, with the results being compared to existing heat transfer correlations [57]. Future work should also concentrate on the optimization of ram air channel components such as the diffuser and nozzle. In particular, the development of advanced operational strategies and control concepts is needed for dynamic operation.

Nomenclature

List of Symbols

Symbol	Description
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DV	Directional Valve
EXV	Expansion Valve
FC	Fuel Cell
GWP	Global Warming Potential
ODP	Ozone Depletion Potential
PEMFC	Proton-Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell
SAF	Synthetic Aviation Fuels

Latin Symbols

Symbol	Description	Unit
A	area	m ²
c_D	drag coefficient	1
c_p	specific isobaric heat capacity	J/(kg K)
c_v	specific isochoric heat capacity	J/(kg K)
D	drag	N
F	thrust	N
g	gravitational acceleration	m/s ²
$k \cdot A$	heat transfer capacity	W/K
L	lift	N
L/D	lift to drag ratio	1
\dot{m}	mass flow rate	kg/s
m	mass	kg
Ma	Mach number	1
P	power	W
p	pressure	Pa
\dot{Q}	heat flux	W
R_i	specific gas constant	J/(kg K)
T	temperature	°C
V	Voltage	V
W	gravitational force	N
w	velocity	m/s

Greek Symbols

Symbol	Description	Unit
α	heat transfer coefficient	W/(m ² K)
η	efficiency	1
κ	isentropic exponent, ratio of c_p/c_v	1
ρ	density	kg/m ³
Θ	nondimensional fuel cell heat flux	1

Subscripts

Symbol	Description
0	entry of ram air channel
1	entry of heat exchanger in ram air channel
2	exit of heat exchanger in ram air channel
3	exit of ram air channel
amb	environment
core	core drag
D	drag
diff	diffuser
el	electric
ext	external drag
fc	fuel cell
front	frontal
h	heated
ideal	ideal
mass	mass drag
MRJE	Meredith-Ram-Jet-Effect
noz	nozzle
out	exit
sub	subpressure drag
t	total pressure / total temperature
th	thermoneutral in relation to maximum thermo-dynamical cell voltage
tot	total
uh	unheated

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan Friedrich Hellmuth: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Philipp Rainer Menke:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Arne Graf von Schweinitz:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Patrick Koschel:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Wilhelm Tegethoff:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Michael Heere:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Christiane Thomas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Jürgen Köhler:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Derivation of the calculation of state variables inside the ram air channel

The absolute temperature of a fluid is defined by the temperature that can be reached adiabatically when the fluid is at rest. The relationship between the static temperature T , the absolute temperature T_t and the flow velocity w is defined by the energy theorem [36]:

$$c_p * T_t = c_p * T + \frac{w^2}{2} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

By transforming and applying the definitions of the specific isobaric heat capacity and the Mach number:

$$c_p = \frac{\kappa * R_t}{\kappa - 1} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$Ma = \frac{w}{\sqrt{\kappa * R_t * T}} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

the expression for the total temperature results in:

$$T_t = T * \left(1 + \frac{\kappa - 1}{2} * Ma^2\right) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

By applying a reversible adiabatic (isentropic) change of state [58]:

$$T * p^{-\frac{\kappa-1}{\kappa}} = \text{constant} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

the relationship between temperature and pressure change is obtained. With the use of Eq. (A.4) and Eq. (A.5), the ratio of absolute pressure p_t and static pressure p is calculated:

$$\frac{p_t}{p} = \left(1 + \frac{\kappa - 1}{2} * Ma^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

In a loss-free (ideal) process, the total pressure remains constant.

$$p_{t,0} = p_{t,1} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

However, the actual processes at the inlet and outlet of the ram air duct are irreversible. To simplify matters, it is assumed that the losses can be approximated using a constant efficiency factor. This means that not all the dynamic pressure at the inlet can be converted into static pressure and not all the static pressure difference at the outlet can be converted into dynamic pressure.

By setting up the equations for the static pressure at the inlet and outlet, the maximum possible pressure difference in the loss-free case can be determined taking Eq. (A.7) into account (i.e., the total pressures in both states are the same), which means that the following applies to the diffuser:

$$(p_1 - p_0)_{\text{ideal}} = p_{t,0} * \left(\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_1^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_0^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} \right) \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The efficiency in the diffuser describes the ratio between the pressure difference actually recovered and the maximum possible pressure difference:

$$\eta_{\text{diff}} = \frac{(p_1 - p_0)}{(p_1 - p_0)_{\text{ideal}}} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Eqs. (A.8) and (A.9) can thus be used to determine the pressure difference including the losses across the diffuser:

$$(p_1 - p_0) = \eta_{\text{diff}} * p_{t,0} * \left(\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_1^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_0^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} \right)$$

$$(A.10)$$

The pressure dependence of κ is low, so that a constant isentropic exponent for air with $\kappa = 1.4$ is assumed.

The equation for the nozzle is analogous to Eq. (A.8) for the diffuser:

$$(p_3 - p_2)_{\text{ideal}} = p_{t,2} * \left(\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_3^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_2^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} \right) \quad (A.11)$$

In terms of efficiency, the direction of action is reversed compared to the diffuser. This means that a greater pressure difference is required to recover the same amount of kinetic energy:

$$\eta_{\text{noz}} = \frac{(p_3 - p_2)_{\text{ideal}}}{(p_3 - p_2)} \quad (A.12)$$

Substituting Eq. (A.12) into Eq. (A.11) yields the following relationship between pressure difference and velocities:

$$(p_3 - p_2) = \frac{p_{t,2}}{\eta_{\text{noz}}} * \left(\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_3^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_2^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} \right) \quad (A.13)$$

Since the nozzle is not defined by a fixed geometry, but rather by the constant outlet pressure, the outlet velocity must be determined. Solving (A.13) for the speed of sound Ma_3 (determined by the relative exit velocity of the air) produces:

$$Ma_3 = \sqrt{\frac{2 * \left(\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_2^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}}} - \frac{(p_2 - p_3) * \eta_{\text{noz}}}{p_{t,2}}} - 1 \right)}{\kappa - 1}} \quad (A.14)$$

The conditions in the ram air channel can be determined on the basis of the relationships described above. Assuming that the static pressure at the diffuser inlet corresponds to the ambient pressure,

$$p_0 = p_{\text{amb}} \quad (A.15)$$

by Eq. (A.6) the absolute pressure at the diffuser entrance $p_{t,0}$ is given by:

$$p_{t,0} = p_0 * \left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_0^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}} \quad (A.16)$$

The static pressure at the outlet of the diffuser p_1 can be directly calculated with Eq. (A.10). To calculate the temperature, the input temperature of the diffuser is also equated with the ambient temperature.

$$T_0 = T_{\text{amb}} \quad (A.17)$$

The temperature change results from the application of the first law of thermodynamics. By balancing with the assumptions that no heat or work is supplied and the volume of the diffuser is constant, as well as that the ram air channel is installed horizontally, the following results for the diffuser [58]:

$$\dot{U} = 0 = \dot{m} * \left(\Delta h + \frac{\Delta w^2}{2} \right) \quad (A.18)$$

We use the enthalpy-temperature correlation:

$$\Delta h = c_p * \Delta T \quad (A.19)$$

At the inlet of the diffuser, it is assumed that the velocity of the air corresponds to the airspeed.

$$w_0 = w_{\text{amb}} \quad (A.20)$$

Fig. B.17. Polarization plot of a pristine 5 kW automotive fuel cell stack traced after Pahon et al. [27].

The cross-sectional area A in the states 1 and 2 is the frontal area of the heat exchanger. The cross-sectional area at the inlet in the 0-state can be adjusted via an adjustable flap of the diffuser. The resulting ratio between input and output cross-section A_0/A_1 is set during operation via a controller and also defines the speed ratio. The speed w_1 can be determined via the relationship between mass flow rate \dot{m} , density ρ and cross-sectional area A :

$$w_1 = \frac{\dot{m}_1}{\rho_1 * A_1} \quad (A.21)$$

The change of state from 1 to 2 takes place via the condenser. The calculations of the states are carried out within the simulation model of the condenser. This is taken as given for the consideration of the ram air channel in this chapter. In general, the absolute temperature is increased and the absolute pressure is reduced.

$$p_{t,2} = p_2 * \left(1 + \frac{\kappa-1}{2} * Ma_2^2\right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa-1}} \quad (A.22)$$

The static pressure p_2 and velocity w_2 is known from the heat exchanger calculation. For the next change of state from 2 to state 3, the process occurring in the diffuser is reversed. It is assumed that the air expands completely in the nozzle and that the outlet pressure of the nozzle corresponds to the ambient pressure.

$$p_3 = p_0 \quad (A.23)$$

The temperature of the air in the state 3 is calculated analogously to its calculation in the diffuser using Eqs. (A.18) and (A.19). The last remaining state variable is the exit velocity from the ram air channel w_3 with ca be determined by rearranging Eq. (A.3) to yield:

$$w_3 = Ma_3 * \sqrt{\kappa * R_1 * T_3} \quad (A.24)$$

with Ma_3 calculated with Eq. (A.14).

Appendix B. Derivation of the empirical formula for fuel cell heat output

Fig. B.17 shows the cell voltage and the resulting power density for a pristine 5 kW automotive PEM fuel cell stack, as it was obtained by Pahon et al. [27] by extracting 17 data pairs of reported voltage and current density. From this data, using Eqs. (3) and (4), for every operating point of the stack, a corresponding heat power density can be calculated.

Normalizing both electrical power density and heat power density to the rated power density of 1.0602 W/cm² creates a dataset of generic fuel cell operation points expressed as the fuel cell utilization degree x and the corresponding normalized fuel cell heat output θ . This dataset with 17 data pairs is shown as a solid line in Fig. B.18.

Fig. B.18. Normalized heat output of an automotive fuel cell stack [27] as a function of degree of fuel cell utilization. The dashed line represents interpolation polynomial used in this study's model for fuel cell heat output calculation. The full polynomial function and root mean square error are displayed in the top of the graph.

For a smooth interpolation within the available data, a 6th order polynomial regression was utilized, creating the empirical expression for θ used to determine the fuel cell heat output in this study's model (Eq. (5)). θ is displayed in Fig. B.18 as a dotted line.

The complete polynomial of θ can be seen in Fig. B.18, as well. A coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.9992$ is achieved.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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